

The influence of gender stereotypes on women's spatial abilities and their underrepresentation in the field of engineering

Malkogeorgou, Styliani

Technological University of Dublin, Ireland

Duffy, Gavin

Technological University of Dublin, Ireland

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ABSTRACT

Technological innovation and scientific progress are important components for improving human condition and economic success. Therefore, a workforce that includes a critical amount of experts in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) domains is needed. Evidence supports that males and females often present differences in their performance and preferences towards some STEM courses and occupations, especially engineering. Specifically, the number of women that decide to pursue careers in the engineering field is relatively low. One possible factor contributing to this gender gap that has gained a lot of interest recently is gender stereotyping and distinct gender roles among societies. Segregation between women and men's societal roles result in psychological gender differences, emerging from early childhood, and can later affect career choices. Additionally, different gender related standards imposed by the society drive women towards activities, majors and careers perceived as more "feminine". Another way gender stereotypes contribute to these differences is by affecting the development of cognitive skills that are hugely involved in engineer learning and thinking. Spatial abilities are part of such skills that play an important role in academic and occupational achievements in STEM domains, is strongly correlated with engineering education and can, on average, be less developed among women relative to men. In this paper we are going to review the literature on the influence of gender stereotypes on women's spatial ability development, and how this may later prevent them from pursuing a career in engineering.

1 INTRODUCTION

The topic of women's underrepresentation in certain science and engineering fields continue to attract the interest of many scholars [1][2]. Even though, women outpace men in higher education, earning 57% of all baccalaureate degrees, some disciplines remain sharply gender segregated. This phenomenon is very evident in engineering, an area where women complete approximately 19% of undergraduate degrees [1]. There are few explanations for the high rates of attrition among women, for example: 1) the chilly or unwelcoming environments that women come across and drive them to exit these majors [1][3]; 2) gender stereotypical approaches towards career among societies, for example people often paint certain professions and activities as masculine and other feminine [1][4]; 3) spatial abilities [3][4]. In general, segregation between genders and strong gender stereotypes among societies do influence a person's view of themselves and their perspectives, and ultimately their behaviour and participation in certain activities that contribute to their development[1][4]. These influences are observable from a very young age, even from 5 or 6 year old. Moreover, girls who are strongly influenced by their social role might not participate in activities (e.g., playing with blocks, using tools) that embrace the development of cognitive skills that play an important role in engineering learning and thinking [4]. While the levels of general intelligence do not differ between men and women, gender differences are sometimes present in more specific cognitive abilities. In particular, spatial abilities are one of the cognitive abilities that present the largest gender gap; on an average level men tend to outperform women in spatial abilities tasks [3][4]. In the following review we are first going to cover the important role of spatial abilities in STEM education, followed by the gender stereotypes, and then how the gender stereotypes may affect women's participation in engineering.

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1 Spatial Abilities & STEM

Early expertise in spatial abilities in children builds the foundation for the development of quantitative reasoning, a collective term encompassing science and mathematics. According to literature, early differences in spatial abilities show important implications for students' achievements in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) fields [3]. But what exactly do we mean with the term spatial abilities; Linn and Petersen [5] defined spatial ability as the "skill in representing, transforming, generating and recalling symbolic, non-linguistic information". In other words, it includes the ability to realise and perceive spatial connections, to visualise spatial related stimuli like objects, and be able to transform or manipulate them – for example using mental rotation to imagine how an object would appear from a different point of view or perspective [3]. Therefore, it is understandable how these skills are important in STEM curricula, since tasks in these fields include identifying, explaining, and classifying the shape, position,

and orientation of objects; manipulating spatial representations in the form of diagrams, graphs, or scientific models; picturing the processes of objects' movement in 3D coordinates; and tangling non-spatial phenomena by using spatial-thinking strategies [3].

Moreover, evidence from longitudinal studies strongly support this link between spatial abilities and STEM [6][7][8]. This evidence demonstrate that: (a) spatial abilities are a "salient psychological characteristic" to advance educational achievements in STEM among young people, who subsequently succeed in similar fields later in life; (b) spatial abilities are involved in shaping the academic and occupational outcomes for intellectually talented individuals and the general population; (c) recent talent searches lose many intellectually talented individuals by limiting their selection criteria to verbal and mathematical abilities measures [6][7]; and (d) students with higher spatial abilities show more interest towards STEM related subjects [8]. In addition to these longitudinal studies, research has highlighted the correlation between spatial abilities and mathematics [9], physics [10], computer science [11], geometry [12], chemistry [13], and engineering [14][15]. Therefore, it is understandable why this topic has drawn the attention of numerous researchers, and why the gender differences in this area pose a concern.

Prior research that focused on gender differences in spatial abilities have made the following observations: (a) not all categories of spatial abilities present gender differences, (b) most gender differences are in mental rotation tasks, (c) once gender differences are found they are detectable across the lifespan [5]. Due to evidence supporting that spatial abilities can be trained and improved via interventions, practice and training [16] and there seems to be a developmental progression of these differences through childhood with an increase later in adulthood, most researchers argue the gender gap is a result of social influences and sociocultural processes more so than biological changes [4]. Research has shown that gender differences in spatial abilities are due to gender differences in spatial experience, for example playing with spatial toys and participating in spatial school subjects [16]. These ideas created the foundations for socio-cultural theories, where the relevance of the stereotyping factor is clear [4]. Especially in late childhood, gender stereotypes offer a reasonable explanation for the gender differences in spatial abilities; and considering the implications of spatial abilities in STEM domains it can also explain females' underrepresentation in some of these fields [3].

2.2 Gender Stereotypes

One commonly held stereotypical belief is that spatial ability is an inherently male aptitude, that males are naturally gifted in this ability. In the long term, these beliefs regarding the masculinity of spatial abilities potentially result in gender differences in spatial achievements by affecting the consistency of how often girls and boys participate in spatial activities at home and school and by influencing

their self-concept of ability [4][16]. Example of spatial activities that contribute in the development of spatial abilities include playing team sports and engaging with workshop activities, such as practicing with tools and repairs. Different gender socialisation may encourage boys to participate more in these activities than girls [16]. Moreover, in the short term, gender stereotypes, by activating negative or positive beliefs about a boy's or a girl's abilities, could result in performance differences between males and females during a spatial test situation [4].

The influence of gender stereotypes has similar effects in some STEM courses. For example, a general idea that boys are better than girls in mathematics might affect girl's performance in math tests and make them internalise this perceived general group characteristic ("girls are bad at maths") as a personal characteristic ("I must be bad at maths"); which of course is not true. Children from the age of 6 are aware of the existence of stereotypes and make important steps towards the development of self-concepts and abilities; and stereotypical beliefs are already present by the age of 10 [4]. It appears that boys and girls from young age adopt behaviours and characteristics in order to fit their gender roles as imposed by society, according to psycho-social theories [4]. The power of stereotypes can be very salient, they can occur unconsciously, get internalised and affect one's image and behaviour without the person realising it.

2.3 The Role of Stereotypes in Engineering

Gender stereotypes towards the field of engineering potentially affect women's participation in this field. Stereotypical claims portray engineering as a masculine domain and project the male dominance in this field [2]. Even though, women are more involved in the field than they used to be and they have made great contributions, based on stereotypes engineering is still commonly considered to be more suitable for men [2]; making women to often feel the need to prove themselves in the field. There is one issue which is often overlooked in this topic, it is the fact that women are not equally underrepresented in all engineering majors; but most of the studies do not specify in which fields women are more underrepresented [1]. For example, in 2013, women completed 40.6% of biomedical engineering degrees, and 36% of chemical engineering degrees, but they comprised only 13% of degrees in electrical and mechanical engineering [1]. The bigger percentage of women in the biomedical and chemical majors, suggests an interesting contrast within the area.

The reason for that could be explained by a theory suggesting gender dualistic approaches among practicing engineers. This dualistic thinking fits engineering practices, jobs, and even personal identities into mutually exclusive categories, for example: 1) technical versus social, 2) hard versus soft, 3) even abstract versus applied [1]. Although, not inherently gendered, the more technical, hard and abstract factors are tailored to the cultural understandings of masculinity, hence more suitable for men, while the social, soft and applied ones are perceived more feminine, hence more suitable for women [17].

In their study Blosser [1] observed that engineer faculty members give feminine or masculine characteristics to different disciplines and then imply that women's seemingly natural taste and proclivities guide them to choose accordingly. For example, faculty members pointed out that biological and industrial engineering carry communication and socially relevant characteristics and this assumingly would attract more women and justify their presence in a major. On the other hand, the future workplace from the male dominated majors were considered by the faculty members as technical and dirty, characteristics that were deemed unappealing for female students [1]. Giving certain activities and majors feminine or masculine identities influence how women's, and generally people's, abilities and preferences are perceived from both their own and other people's perspectives [2].

3 SUMMARY

In conclusion, cultural stereotypes about gender differences are still influencing people's view, assisting to the maintenance of segregation between men and women across professional fields [1][2]. Of course, women are able to and do embrace parts of engineering that are considered more masculine. However, normative standards of appropriate masculine and feminine behaviour stand as guides and people are expecting to be judged by them; therefore, this leads to behaviour alterations in order to keep social sanctions to the minimum and adopt ways that are consistent with cultural understandings of the gender roles [1]. These risky notions drive women to avoid masculine engineering fields, as well as the opposite, it can drive them towards feminine fields by projecting their biased assessments of their abilities and strengths, by both themselves and others [1][5]. There is a need to understand that these stereotypical behaviours and ways of thinking do not suddenly emerge when people choose their majors, but rather start very early on throughout the development of a person's identity, from childhood to adulthood. Educators need to take under consideration the impact of gender socialization in a person's abilities and preferences, and how this can be changed and reshaped.

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